

Appendix I: Questionnaire for customers and operational staff of NWSC in Bushenyi-Ishaka Municipality.

Hello,

My name is Tumusiime Joannes, and I am currently a student at KIU Western Campus, pursuing a Master of Business Administration degree with a focus on Accounting and Finance. I am conducting a study on "billing systems and customer satisfaction in NWSC in Bushenyi-Ishaka Municipality."

As part of this study, all participants will have the opportunity to review and sign a consent form, which outlines the purpose, goals, and potential risks of the study. I kindly request your participation in this study and appreciate your willingness to answer the questions provided in the following document.

Throughout the study, the researcher will uphold ethical standards by prioritizing the rights of all participants. This includes obtaining informed consent, ensuring anonymity, maintaining confidentiality, respecting privacy, and reporting data honestly. Rest assured that the information provided will be solely used for academic purposes. Thank you for your cooperation.

Thank you for your cooperation.

Sincerely,

Tumusiime Joannes

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

1. Gender:

Male

Female

2. Marital Status:

Single

Married

Others, please specify: _____

3. Age Bracket (years):

- a. 20 and below
- b. 20 to 29 years
- c. 30 to 39 years
- d. 40 years and above

4. Level of Education:

- a) No formal education
- b) Primary
- c) Secondary education
- d) Certificate
- e) Tertiary education
- f) Postgraduate education
- c) Diploma

5. Types of customers

- a) Residential customer
- b) Commercial customer
- c) Institutional customer
- d) Industrial customer

6. Duration as a customer

- a) Less than 1 year
- b) 1 – 3 years
- c) 4 – 6 years

d) 7 – 10 years

e) More than 10 years

SECTION B: Billing systems in NWSC

In this section, a scale of 1-5 will be used, you are advised to tick appropriately in accordance to your choice with the following statements.

Key: 1 –Disagree Strongly (DS), 2 – Disagree (D), 3 – Not sure (NS), 4 – Agree (A) and 5 –Agree Strongly (AS).

Statement	DS	D	NS	A	AS
Prepaid billing system					
Prepaid system allows customers to use water only when they have credited their water accounts					
Prepaid system has enabled customers of NWSC to self-manage their water accounts					
Prepaid billing system has empowered customers to control the cost of water they use					
Prepaid water meters will reduced many customer complaints since customer accounts are self-managed					
Pre-paid billing allows customers independency in water usage and divisibility of buying water					
Pre-paid billing system reduces costs because the meter readers have reduced burden of visiting homes occasionally to have metre readings					
Postpaid billing system					
Customer meters are read on a monthly basis					
Postpaid meters enable customers to pay their bills in time					
NWSC normally disconnect customers when they don't pay in time					

Monthly water paper bills are delivered to customer premises in time every month					
Customers always pay exact amount of water used					
Water users are charged disconnection fees when they fail to pay water dues in time and National water staff distributing water bills are always friendly					
billing accuracy and transparency	DS	D	NS	A	AS
My water bill accurately reflects my actual water usage.					
I find the billing statements provided by the water utility clear and easy to understand.					
I receive my water bills on a regular and consistent basis without delays.					
The water utility provides sufficient advance notice of any changes in billing rates or policies.					
I have easy access to detailed information about my water usage and charges through customer service or online platforms.					
The water utility resolves billing discrepancies quickly and effectively					

Section: Customer Satisfaction

Statement	DS	D	NS	A	AS
A number of referrals from old clients have been witnessed in NWSC and NWSC water supply is reliable					
NWSC staff clearly explains to the customers before supply is disconnected (customer care)					
NWSC responds in time whenever a complaint is logged in and treats customers fairly					
The reception area at NWSC Bushenyi is welcoming					
Customers call customer care centers for assistance					
The staffs in NWSC make emphasis on how customers with complaints should be handled politely					

I am glad for Your Precious Time